

**MUSIC IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION**

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Abstract. *In this article, the role of music in our cultural life, the importance of music in the formation of personality, the spiritual and moral image of a music teacher and the modern demands placed on him, the opinions of eastern thinkers about the development of the art of music are discussed.*

Key words: music, culture, art, education, theory, creator, school, methodology

МУЗЫКА В РАЗВИТИИ ЛИЧНОСТИ РОЛЬ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются роль музыки в нашей культурной жизни, значение музыки в формировании личности, духовно-нравственный облик учителя музыки и современные требования, предъявляемые к нему, мнения восточных мыслителей о развитии музыкального искусства.*

Ключевые слова: музыка, культура, искусство, образование, теория, творец, школа, методика.

Music is an art form that occupies a large place in our cultural life and is of great importance in the development of human personality. Family, school, and society are of great importance in the spiritual formation of every person. Because the characteristics of human humanity are found in society. Along with many educational factors, music education has a special place in leading the young generation to maturity.

Music education is one of the main and complex aspects of the education of sophistication, it teaches a person to correctly perceive and appreciate the beautiful things around him. Music has the ability to strongly influence the human psyche, and is an important means of introducing it to the world of sophistication and moral and ideological education. Music equips a person with high taste and gives him spiritual nourishment. The main goal of teaching music at school is to form a musical culture in students and make them mature people who can meet the demands of the times.

The main tasks of teaching music lessons at school are as follows:

- to increase students' interest and love for the art of music;
- in the process of musical activities, to develop musical abilities of students, musical learning, voice, attention and feelings of creativity;
- to educate in an ethical and aesthetic spirit through the artistic and ideological content of musical works;
- in music lessons, to direct students to a profession, to form love for work, love for the Motherland, and respect for adults.

The realization of these goals and tasks depends on the teacher's professional and pedagogical skills. Not every artist can teach music culture classes at school. For this, a music teacher must have mastered pedagogy, psychology, physiology of colors, music teaching and methodology, as well as his musical profession. A music teacher should be a person who loves his profession and children, has a high culture and a broad outlook.

Our wise people have understood since time immemorial that melodies and songs can quickly find a way to the heart of a child, have a positive effect on the psyche, and the qualities of good manners and manners, kindness, patience, and respect for adults are formed through music.

In the family, teaching a child to sing and play music was considered a parent's dream. A child gets acquainted with music through his mother and receives lifelong nourishment from music. Because the child, before he can walk and talk, listens to the music and expresses his reaction to the music with various hand movements.

That is why it has been a tradition in every family to keep a dutor, circle, and rubob from musical instruments. In order to get nourishment from music, a person must be a person with a pure heart, a high spirituality, and a person who can feel beauty. "The future of any society depends on the youth, the future of building a great state, and how they are educated.

The future of our people, the perspective of independent Uzbekistan depends in many ways on the teacher's worldview, preparation, selflessness, and his attitude to the work of teaching and educating the young generation. Today's demand is to strengthen the professional training of future music teachers, teach them about their specialties, acquire pedagogical skills, and teach them how to apply theoretical knowledge in practice.

In connection with the implementation of the continuous pedagogical education system, the focus is on teacher training and teacher retraining. The teaching profession is an honorable, but very complicated profession, a teacher must master the theory of music, love children, and have experience in pedagogical practice. Because the pedagogical process in school life is very diverse.

This requires thorough knowledge, practical training, high pedagogical skills and creativity from the music teacher. A future music teacher should have a culture of dress and a culture of speech.

He loves the teaching profession and children, and helps them to grow into full-fledged human beings. should use handouts. Having mastered his professional specialty, being able to adapt his voice to the voice of children, having performance skills, actively participating in various contests and events by attracting students to extracurricular clubs.

It is important for the teacher to step in step with the times along with the screenwriter, artist, performer and director of each lesson. In order to become a teacher, it is necessary to be physically and mentally healthy along with professional skills. "We need to raise a healthy generation and bring it to adulthood," states our President I.A. Karimov¹. "Healthy person" means not only physical health, but also a person with a healthy mental character, matured in the spirit of oriental manners and universal ideals."

The great pedagogue A. Avioniy said, "Educators are like a doctor, a doctor is a patient in the body. just as he cures the disease, the teacher also influences the mental development of the child through music and brings up in them such feelings as purity, conscience, loyalty, kindness,

respect for adults, and love for the Motherland. "Education is either life or death for us, salvation or destruction. It's a matter of either happiness or disaster," he wrote.

The great thinker poet A. Navoi deeply studied the aspects of music education in his works and said: "Music is an important basis of community life.

Only music brings clarity, balance and a sense of self-confidence to a person's heart and makes him happy" A1 Farobi thinks: "Music is a rare art, a force that leads to goodness", "Whoever wants to learn knowledge and wisdom, first of all, he should achieve spiritual perfection" - says Abu Raykhan Beruni. "Whoever says that he has learned wisdom, let his child learn from a young age, from learned and wise people, only then he will reach the level of perfection"; Therefore, at the present time, the responsibility of the music teacher, a new approach to science requires a deep study of its methodology.

In general education schools, the main goal of music culture lessons is to create content of musical culture as a means of arousing interest in music in students. Because under the influence of melody and melody, a person develops feelings of striving for goodness, preserving beauty, love for mother nature, motherland, and enriches his spiritual world.

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